

DIAGNOSIS OF LUNG CANCER BY USING HRCT, DRUG DISCOVERY BY USING HAEMOTOLOGY AND MICROSCOPY TECHNIQUES UNDER THE ANALYTE LEVODOR

Ayesha Jabeen¹, Sadia Malik^{*2}, Kiran Aslam³, Arooj Shaheen⁴, Saima Batool⁵, Munir Malik⁶,
Dr. Farooque Ahmad Haidari⁷, Hafeez Ullah⁸, Afshan Shahzadi⁹, Kinza Saleem¹⁰

^{1,2,3,5} Department of Physics, Government Sadiq College Women University Bahawalpur.

⁹Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur (BVH).

¹⁶ MINAR (Multan Institute of Nuclear oncology and Radiology).

^{3,4,8}Institute of Physics, Islamia University Bahawalpur.

²Sadia.malik@gscwu.edu.pk

²<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2319-4373>

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Sadia Malik

Abstract

Using the high resolution computed tomography (HRCT) technology, we may obtain an inside image of several human organs using X-rays. This method is being used in this instance to diagnose lung cancer or a lung mass. Different techniques are used to diagnose various diseases, however after utilizing the HRCT technique, it is discovered that it gives us a thorough and detailed view of the body's organs, which is quite helpful for spotting pathology. Blood haematology is considerably applicable with the inclusion of LEVODOR, an anti-cancerous substance. After each dose, blood slides are prepared in order to examine the effects of LEVODOR.

Utilizing White light digital microscopy or dark field microscopy, the changes in blood parameters following the addition of the analyte will be seen.

INTRODUCTION

High-resolution computed tomography is known as HRCT. Actually, it is a straight Forward computed tomography or CT scan routine. In this method, we employed radiations to get pictures of several human organs in order to identify or diagnose the pathology of a disease. It is utilized for the identification of covid-19, lung cancer, lung mass, and brain tumors

The trachea, the major airway (bronchus), or the lung tissue is where lung cancer first appears. The chest radiograph does have certain restrictions, though. In

10 to 15 percent of those experiencing symptoms, it is typical to have nearly 60% of individuals with emphysema have documented infiltrative lung disease, as do up to 30% of those with bronchiectasis [1]. Chest radiographs have been demonstrated to have an overall sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 82 % for detecting diffuse lung disease in various investigations [2]. Only 23% of patients could be confidently diagnosed by chest radiography, and only 77% of those instances had the proper diagnosis. These factors make

high resolution computed tomography (HRCT, also known as thin-section CT scanning) a popular tool for examination of certain issues. Obstructive or restrictive pulmonary function tests are correlated with typical characteristics of the small airways and the lung parenchyma [3]. When compared to chest radiography or traditional CT scanning, HRCT frequently offers more information due to its high sensitivity and specificity (95-100%) [2, 4- 7]. The chosen thin slice is 122 mm in width. We reduce the field of vision by employing high definition images in order to reduce the size of each pixel. The scan speed may be

adjusted to maximize resolution for all other parameters.

Methodology:

The computed tomography (CT) examinations were conducted using a Toshiba Aquilion Prime 160 slice scanner, operating at a voltage of 412V with direct homogeneous technology. The scan protocol employed a slice thickness of 1 mm, with axial body scans acquired in 3.5 seconds. Contrast enhancement was achieved using iodinated agents, **specially Omnipaque and Ultravist.**

Figure 1: Shows the internal structure and components. Flow diagram which shows the whole procedure of getting image at computer screen.

In next approach, a CCD camera is utilized to record pictures in transmission mode while using white light digital microscopy and dark field microscopy (where the area surrounding the object is dark). In light microscopy, the sample will fluoresce as a result of a strong stream of light being delivered.

With the use of a hematological analyzer called a celltac- α , mix five different doses of levodopa into malignant blood from 0g to 150g into 3mL blood in five distinct test tubes to complete CBC.

ANALYTE:

WE are going to use an anti-cancerous medicine named as levofloxacin as a hemihydrates.

The CBC (complete blood cell count) report will be generated by this method. Additionally, it will give complete details on all blood parameters both before and after the addition of the analyte.

Prepare slides of each sample, then examine them under a light microscope to obtain pictures that will allow you to see how Levodopa effect the blood cell counts. It contains the form and quantity of the blood components vary over time.

Results and discussions:

The visual pictures of a few patients are displayed below after using the HRCT technique on several patients in the Radiology department of Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital. To view these pictures in preview, utilize Radiant Viewer.

Figure 2: HRCT images of different patients.

CHANGES IN BLOOD PARAMETERS:

We mixed three milliliters of blood with five different doses of Levodopa—0, 20, 50, 100, and 150 milliliters—and performed a CBC using a hematological analyzer called a celltac. The following table lists the findings we gleaned from the reports.

Sr no.	Concentration of analyte (mg)	No of RBC's (10 ⁶ /μL)	No of WBC's (10 ³ /μL)	HGB (g/dL)	HCT (%)	MCV (fL)	MCH (fL)	MCHC (fL)	PLT (10 ³ /μL)
1	0	14.3	4.20	9.9	34.3	81.7	23.6	28.9	455
2	20	14.4	4.23	9.9	34.7	82.0	23.4	28.5	451
3	50	13.7	4.16	9.9	34.4	82.7	23.8	28.8	441
4	100	14.5	4.26	9.9	35.2	82.6	23.2	28.1	418
5	150	13.1	4.27	10.1	35.5	83.1	23.7	28.5	420

Conc. Of Analyte (mg)	Size of cell (i)	Size of cell (ii)	Average size
0	1.02"		1.02"
20	0.92"	0.81"	0.865"
50	0.85"	0.69"	0.77"
100	0.48"	0.56"	0.52"
150	0.56"	0.52"	0.54"

Changes in size of WBC'S:

Figure 3: the graphs are showing the variations in blood parameters.

Figure 4: Microscopic slides showing the change in the size of WBC'S.

Conclusion:

After researching high resolution computed tomography (HRCT) and using it to thoroughly examine the Cases of many patients, we discover that it is a highly helpful technology for diagnosing a variety of illnesses, particularly diffuse lung diseases like lung cancer. We discover that the HRCT technology gives us a thorough, clear, and complete view of the required body sections, which has been shown to be quite

beneficial in the diagnosis of disease by looking at the scan reports of various patients.

Therefore, the HRCT technique is quite helpful for identifying disease in many human organs, and it is also a simple, quick, and painless approach. Thus, while not regularly, we can use it. After undergoing

this procedure once, we must wait at least 90 days before scheduling the following scan.

Hematology plays an essential role in understanding and managing lung cancer. By analyzing blood cells and observing how different analytes affect them, this technique provides useful clues about the disease status. It supports clinicians in assessing the stage of lung cancer and in selecting the most suitable treatment plan for patients. Levodopa is an analyte which is showing anti cancer characters due to which it can be used as a medicine for lung cancer.

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